

Is the Classical Notion of Impulse Based on Quantum Mechanics?

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The idea of impulse, i.e. Change in momentum = Integral dt Force appears in Newtonian mechanics. Impulse is considered to be a physical observable, for example it may be linked to the damage done by a particle hitting a target. Impulse, however, only depends on momentum and so two particles with the same momentum, but different masses and velocities may cause the same damage i.e. represent the same physical observable. Momentum in nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics is $m v$ where m is rest mass and v velocity. Velocity requires a clock in order to measure it, yet two particles with the same momentum and different velocities are considered equivalent in terms of the damage done upon collision with a target i.e the physical impulse. Thus we suggest that time must formally disappear from mv , but this implies that rest mass must behave as t or dt . Furthermore, given Kinetic energy = $.5mv^2$, it must behave as $1/dt$. In other words, the reciprocal of kinetic energy behaves as a gradation of time. This is not a standard clock as the gradation is based on a specific kinetic energy and is different for another. In other words, two particles with the same p and different v , have different time gradations. This, however, is a quantum mechanical result. Thus we argue that quantum mechanics may be responsible for the idea of p yielding the same impulse hit for two different v .

We further argue that these ideas may be extended to include rest mass with $v=0$ and to indicate that $1/p$ is linked to dx , a ruler gradation which is again a quantum mechanical result. Lastly, we argue that these ideas lead to the special relativistic result $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$ and so argue that free particle quantum mechanics and special relativity are closely linked and that classical impulse follows from free particle quantum mechanics.

Impulse in Classical Newtonian Mechanics

Impulse is defined as a physical observable in Newtonian mechanics (just as force is a physical observable i.e. a push or a pull). It is associated with the damage or strength of a collision between a particle with constant momentum p and a target. Formally it is defined as:

$$\text{Impulse} = \int dp = \int \text{Force} dt \quad ((1))$$

((1)) implies that two particles bouncing off a target i.e. $p \rightarrow -p$, but having different rest masses and velocities should impart the same physical impulse. Thus one may physically observe and measure their different velocities, but in terms of the impulse collision, they are identical. Velocity requires a clock for its measurement, but it seems momentum should not if two particles with the same mass and different velocities are identical with respect to the impulse of a collision. Thus we suggest that time should formally disappear from the nonrelativistic mv formula. This implies rest mass m must have units of t or dt and kinetic energy should be proportional to $1/t$ or $1/dt$. (Mass could also have dx pieces as these have nothing to do with time. This will appear in a later section. Here we are only concerned with time.)

In other words, kinetic energy should represent the gradation of a "special clock". Two particles with the same p and different velocities would be associated with different clock gradations. This

seems like an unusual result, but it is the result of quantum mechanics for a free particle i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$. Thus we suggest that impulse being independent of velocity may be a quantum mechanical result manifested in the classical world.

Rest Mass with No Velocity

According to the above argument, rest mass should be proportional to time or dt even if $v=0$. In such a case kinetic energy is 0. For kinetic energy $.5mv^2$, doubling rest mass doubles kinetic energy and halves dt . One would expect the same for a mass at rest. Thus one might postulate:

$$\text{Energy} = m b^2 \text{ where } b \text{ is a constant with units of velocity} \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, kinetic energy is not the full energy of a particle, rather one would suggest:

$$\text{Energy} = m b^2 + .5mv^2 \quad ((3))$$

Thus the concept of energy for a particle suggests an internal clock with gradations equivalent to $1/E$. Even though dx appears in the definition of velocity, for a mass at rest, dx has no meaning.

In other words, the position is completely arbitrary and there is no need for the notion of dx i.e. a ruler gradation as the particle is not moving. Thus we only consider dt as proportional to $1/E$.

If the particle moves at constant v , it has constant momentum. Just as an energy represents running time, one might suggest that a momentum implies a ruler gradation. In other words, even though nonrelativistically it is written as $p=mv$, time disappears, but this form should ultimately yield $1/dx$. Does this follow from the units of energy?

$$\text{Energy} = m_0 dx/dt \quad dx/dt \text{ (in terms of units) and } m_0 \rightarrow dt \text{ so energy} \rightarrow dx \quad dx/dt$$

If $1/E$ goes as dt as a clock gradation, which is implied by a rest mass, for which dx has no meaning, then:

$$m_0 \text{ goes as } dt / (dx \quad dx) \text{ and } p = mv = 1/dx \quad ((4)) \text{ (in terms of units)}$$

Thus, dx a ruler gradation is associated with $1/p$.

As a result, a particle moving with constant v and a given rest mass has an internal clock with gradation linked to $1 / (m_0 b^2 + .5mv^2)$ and an internal ruler with gradations associated with $1/p$. These are quantum mechanical results, following from the classical Newtonian observation that p governs an impulse without the notion of v appearing.

The Case of a Photon

A photon has both energy and momentum as well as a velocity c in a vacuum. Thus according to the above arguments, it should have a built-in clock with gradations proportional to $1/E$ and a built-in ruler with gradations proportional to $1/p$.

In ((2)) we suggested that a rest mass with $v=0$ has an energy given by $m b b$, where b is a velocity. The question is: What is this velocity? If a particle may take on any velocity then it seems unusual to have an arbitrary velocity b . If one, however, postulates that c is the upper bound on the velocity of a particle, then one could suggest $b=c$.

Given that $b=c$ is now a very large number, a typical classical velocity is much less than c . Then ((3)) may be a series expansion with $v \ll c$ i.e

Energy = $m c c + .5 m v v$ might actually be a series expansion of:

$$\text{Energy} = m c c / \sqrt{1 - v v / c c} \quad ((5))$$

One may try to write one equation linking E and p for both a particle with rest mass and photon. In the photon case, $E = p c$ and for a particle $E = m c c / \sqrt{1 - v v / c c}$. Momentum should contain $m v$ and equal it in the $v \ll c$ limit. Squaring ((5)) yields:

$$E * E = m m c c / (1 - v v / c c) = p p c c + m m c c c c \quad ((6))$$

If $m=0$, ((6)) yields the photon result. $P = B(v/c) m v$ so:

$$E E = B B m m v v + m m c c c c = m m c c / (1 - v v / c c) \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that $B B = 1 / (1 - v v / c c)$.

As a result, the idea of impulse being linked to momentum which does not require a clock to measure because it represents the strength of a hit against a target may be argued to follow from free particle quantum mechanics and also lead to some ideas of special relativity suggesting that free particle quantum mechanics and special relativity may be closely linked.

Conclusion

In conclusion, momentum p is defined as $m v$ where m is rest mass and v velocity in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics. One might expect that to compute momentum, one must know velocity and hence use a clock to measure it. In Newtonian mechanics, however, one also has the notion of impulse as a physical observable. It is given by: change in $p = \int dt \text{ Force}$. Two particles with the same momentum, but different rest masses and velocities, hitting a target and bouncing back with $-p$, have the same physical impulse. Thus velocity should not ultimately be needed to know momentum. We argue this implies $p = m v$ should allow for "t" to disappear. This occurs if m_0 is proportional t or dt and it follows that kinetic energy is

proportional to $\frac{dx}{dt}$. In other words, energy goes as $1/dt$ or dt goes as $1/\text{energy}$ which is a quantum mechanical result.

We suggest that one may extend these ideas to a rest mass with $v=0$. In such a case, dx has no meaning because there is no motion. Thus we suggest that in this case: $\text{energy} = \text{rest mass} \cdot b^2$ where b is an unknown velocity. We also suggest that energy goes as $1/dt$ or dt goes as $1/\text{energy}$ defining the gradations of a "special" clock. As a result, one might write overall energy as $mb^2 + .5mv^2$ and argue that it goes as $1/dt$. In the case of momentum, there is motion i.e. a v . If one simply considers the units of $.5mv^2$ and associates it with $1/dt$, then $1/p$ goes as dx , another quantum mechanical result for a free particle.

We next ask: What is b ? If a particle may take on any value v , it is not at all clear what b should be. If on the other hand one limits v to a maximum value of c , the speed of light in a vacuum, we argue these ideas lead to the special relativistic result: $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$ where m is rest mass.

Thus we argue that p yielding the same physical impulse for different velocities and corresponding rest masses (such that all have the same p) follows from the free particle quantum mechanical result that dt go as $1/E$ i.e. a special clock exists with energy related gradations. Momentum may be shown to be linked to dx through $dx \rightarrow 1/p$, albeit in a hand wavy manner. We also argue that special relativity follows from these ideas, in particular $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$